

Assessment of Student Performance in the Context of Active Learning

Ana Carla Bittencourt Reis¹, Milena Rodrigues Santos², Ronaldo Rodrigues Pacheco¹, João Mello da Silva¹

¹ Master Program in Applied Computing University of Brasília (UnB), Brasília, Brazil;

² Department of Industrial Engineering, Faculty of Technology, University of Brasília, Brasília, Brazil

Email: anacarlabr@unb.br, milena.mrsantos@gmail.com, ronaldo.pacheco07.rp@gmail.com, joaomello@unb.br,

Abstract

The growing adherence to the use of active learning methodologies brought to light the discussion of the challenge related to the forms of student assessment used and the performance measurement, expressed by the grades. In this type of approach, team projects are very common, where students are expected to collaborate equitably. For these cases, the forms of assessment practiced involve individual and group assessments, concomitantly or not. For both cases, the challenge remains to extract the contribution of each student from the work developed and express it through evaluations (grades). Given the above, this paper aims to bring a discussion about the theme and the proposal of alternatives that best suit the context of active learning. As a result, in addition to an extensive literature review, presenting the challenges experienced by professors, an evaluation model for Industrial Engineering courses is presented.

Keywords: Active Learning; student performance, student assessment, PBL

1 Introduction

The evaluative practices in active methodologies of education in engineering are the target of discussions by scholars on the subject. On the one hand, there is testing, commonly used in traditional teaching methodologies, with direct ways of assessing the student's knowledge on a given topic. On the other hand, there are active methodologies, which work on the development of so-called soft skills and have in their design a strong appeal for group work, and anticipation of experiences that would be experienced in the labor market.

A report by the American Society for Engineering Education (ASEE, 2009) highlights that, in order to address the growing list of interconnected and complex global problems, it is necessary to train engineers capable of dealing with the multifaceted nature of the challenges of 21st century. It means that the most important thing is not only the technical content learned, but also to be able to properly have ethical attitudes and behaviors, which requires changing traditional classrooms into learning environments, in which contextualized activities are developed and based mainly on active learning (ABENGE, 2018).

It is believed that the traditional classroom approach does not offer engineering students so-called social skills, such as communication, collaboration, personal skills and design skills (Nguyen, 1998). According to Reis et al. (2017), engineering education has been the subject of studies to provide better results in terms of learning. In general, the results point to the development of soft skills, but what has been learned in terms of technical content? How to measure the learning of these contents individually, considering the development of group work? How to measure the development of soft skills by each student? What forms of assessment can be conducted in an active learning environment that safeguard the technical quality (individual) of the engineer? These are some of the questions that researchers and professors who adhere to these methodologies seek to answer and solve in order to promote the best of active learning, ensuring the learning of soft skills and technical concepts.

In order to answer the aforementioned questions, the main objective of this article is to propose a model for assessing student performance, in an active learning context, considering technical aspects and developed skills, and group and individual performance. For this, a systematic literature review is carried out and based on the observation of existing models and the teaching experience in engineering, an evaluation model is proposed.

The article is structured as follows: after the introduction (section 1), the research methodologies (section 2) are presented. Then, the consolidation of the systematic literature review on performance assessment in active learning is presented (Section 3). Subsequently, the proposed model is presented (Section 4). Finally, the final considerations are presented (Section 5).

2 Research methodology

This section presents the methods and structure used in the study to achieve the objectives. The research strategy is classified as a systematic literature review, which, through a qualitative approach, seeks to understand the main elements of the scientific literature to propose a model for assessing performance in active learning.

2.1 Research Structure

Step 1. Research Preparation

In this stage, four essential requirements were established to guide the bibliographic research: the databases used; the terms or keywords; the knowledge areas targeted by the research; and the space-time coverage for selecting works.

As for databases, Web of Science (WoS) was chosen because it is internationally recognized as one of the most complete and reliable. In addition, the Scopus database was used because it is multilingual and has a greater coverage than the first (Zupic and Cater, 2015).

The search terms used were ("PBL" OR "PjBL" OR "project based learning") AND ("assess *" OR "evaluat *" OR "calculat *") AND ("grad *" OR "scor *") AND ("individual" OR "group *" OR "team *") AND ("student *" OR "project *" OR "course *") in order to return only articles that include the integration of terms. The use of the logical operators AND and OR and the elements asterisk (*) and quotation marks ("") is perceived, as they allow greater coverage on the topic while delimiting the findings by the intersections between the terms.

The "research areas" field was defined by Engineering with the timeframe delimited between 2010 and 2020.

Step 2. Survey data

After collecting the data, filtering was performed to eliminate duplicate articles between the bases. Subsequently, the abstracts were read in order to keep only the articles pertinent to the research scope. In addition, for the selection of articles, only the most cited article (given the impact factor) and the most relevant ones published since 2018 were selected.

Step 3. Performance evaluation in active learning

Thus, the main elements present in the main models on performance evaluation of students in active learning environments found in scientific literature were listed. Based on this literature review, a performance evaluation model is proposed.

In Figure 1, the steps carried out in the Research are presented.

Figure 1. Research Structure

3 Performance Evaluation in Active Learning

The importance of assessing student performance is well known, given that assessments, as well as adequate assessment processes, contribute to an effective educational process (Garcia et al, 2008). This need extends to the context of active learning, which is based on the principle that the learning process, unlike traditional teaching, occurs by removing the point of focus from teachers and passing it on to students.

However, despite the many benefits arising from active learning, challenges in assessing individual performance are implied by group projects, since there is a possibility that some individuals could assume a greater workload and, final grades, therefore, may not reflect individual performance (Fernandes, 2014).

3.1 Elements for performance evaluation of an active engineering learning

There are several models developed to assess student performance in subjects and other activities involving active learning. This topic presents some elements found in the literature on the topic, which provided support for the development of the proposed model.

The composition of groups to carry out activities, as mentioned, is a common practice in the active learning disciplines and is observed in several works such as, for example, Arbelaitz et al (2015), Malheiro et al., (2015), Setiawan (2019), Ashworth (2015), De los Ríos-Carmenado et al., (2015), Tao et al (2015), Nguyen et al (2013), Chang et al. (2011), Krpalkova et al (2015).

In the work of Arbelaitz et al (2015), in addition to the group project, individual activities were carried out (15% of the grade composition) focused on assessing knowledge about the subject in question, in the case of this study, programming in C. In group (25% of the grade composition), the core was collaboration using the presentation and the project developed to compose the grade. In addition, it is necessary to obtain at least 30% in the knowledge test.

Chua et al (2013) introduces a method used to assess students composed of three stages: (1) written test to assess knowledge about the topic, (2) oral exams focused on problem solving based on scenarios and, finally, (3) quality testing of the final product project's to assess performance and results.

The case study developed by Fernandes et al (2014), contemplates the development of the project in 17 weeks with well-defined deliveries containing the presentation of the project, a team management strategy, project report (in different phases), formal presentation, written test, discussion and delivery of a poster. The authors confirm the importance of the participants themselves being involved in the evaluation of the project, through peer evaluation, based on criteria, to compose the final grade of each member of the project team.

Malheiro et al., (2015) follow the same line as Fernandes et al (2014), however, in addition to including a product or prototype, they use self-assessment and peer review to fill the gaps in group assessments. The evaluations involve seven dimensions: quality, quantity of technical contribution, openness to new ideas, teamwork performance, leadership, attitude and initiative, with a rating ranging from 1 to 5. Thus, the final grade is made up of both verification of deliveries in groups, corresponding to 35% of the final grade, as well as for individual ones, which is composed of the weighted average of all attributed. These same evaluation criteria were observed in the work of Ashworth (2015), with group evaluations (three oral presentations, at the beginning, middle and end of the project) and individual evaluation to compose the final grade of each student. The author also used peer and self-assessment (35% of the grade).

A work with interesting methodology was presented by Gweon et al., (2015) where the evaluation of two actors was used: the observer and the evaluator. For the grade composition, the average of the weekly evaluations was measured, each evaluation was composed of questions related to five areas (participation, group work, progress, knowledge co-construction and definition of goals).

The methodology proposed by De los Ríos-Carmenado et al., (2015) included 10 types of evaluation (individual and group), each one having a specific weight in the composition of the final grade, they are: lectures, group work outside class, participation in PBL workshops, cooperative learning activities, problem-based learning, relevant activities to the case study, information technology support, group tutoring, online tutoring, self-assessment and continuous assessment.

Unlike most of the reported authors, Tao et al (2015) adhered to the use of written tests to individually assess the student, in addition to the evaluation activities related to the project, such as: abstract, theoretical questions, used methods, project evolution, work in groups and completion of the project. In several other methodologies found in the literature, individual evaluations were used (Kosloski, 2019, Tao et al., 2015, Nguyen et al., 2013, Chang et al., 2011, Herráez & Claver, 2011), oral presentations (Kosloski, 2019), peer review (Chang et al., 2011, Krpalkova et al., 2015)), group work (Tao et al., 2015, Nguyen et al., 2013), self-assessment (Nguyen et al., 2013, Krpalkova et al., 2015), project evaluation (Krpalkova et al., 2015), activities involving the active learning methodology (Herráez & Claver, 2011) and also, project evaluation through software (Chang et al., 2011).

Many of the authors presented above, despite using several evaluation criteria, exhibited difficulties in appropriately assessing the individual performance of students correctly. Malheiros et al (2015) propose that self-assessment and peer review addresses the possible inequalities between grades and actual contributions. Arbeitatz et al (2015), discuss the opportunity to introduce, at the end of the course, some type of evaluation mechanism, which is optional, so that students can improve their final grades.

additionally, Fernandes et al (2014), Setiawan (2019) and Gweon et al (2015), demonstrate a difference between the final grades attributed by the evaluators and the students' perception of what their own should be final grade.

In view of the challenges and difficulties presented, an evaluation model is proposed, due to the composition of different evaluation dimensions, in order to attribute the student's final grade more assertively.

4 Proposed Model for Performance Evaluation

The proposed model for student evaluation in the disciplines that use active learning methodologies is based on the workflow described by Barbalho et al., 2017 (Figure 2). Preliminary Project (PP), Intermediate Project (PI) and Final Project (PF), are used for evaluation in the discipline Production Systems Project 4 (PSP 4) of the Industrial Engineering course at University of Brasília (UnB).

Figure 2. Basic structure of PSP4 (Barbalho et al., 2017).

The proposed model is composed of the elements presented in Table 1 composed by individual, group and peer evaluations. Individual assessments aim to identify students' involvement in projects, as well as their technical development. Group assessments aim to assess what the group was able to develop with the contribution of each individual.

In the three phases (PP, IP, FP) there are three types of assessment, individual, in groups and by peers. In this way, we seek to safeguard individual involvement, but also to value what the group was able to develop together.

Table 1- Elements of proposed model

PP			IP			FP		
Aspects evaluated	Assessed subject	Evaluation	Aspects evaluated	Assessed subject	Evaluation	Aspects evaluated	Assessed subject	Evaluation
Scope Definition	Group	2,5	Proposition of the technical solution	Group	2,5	Technical solution developed (written project)	Group	15
Goal setting	Group	2,5	Description of the company studied	Group	2,5	Formal Presentation	Individual	10
Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) Preparation	Group	2,5	Description of the problem analyzed	Group	2,5	Individual QUIZ	Individual	17,5
Risk Analysis	Group	2,5	Preliminary results of the technical solution	Group	5	Skills development	Individual	2,5
Stakeholder identification and analysis (expectations, power and interest)	Group	2,5	Compliance and adequacy of the schedule	Group	2,5	Final score		45
Development of Communication Artefacts	Group	2,5	Formal Presentation	Individual	5			
Schedule Formulation	Group	2,5	Oral argumentation	Individual	7,5			
Formal Presentation	Individual	2,5	Skills development	Individual	2,5			
Skills development	Individual	2,5	Final score		30			
Oral argumentation	Individual	2,5						
Final score		25						

As noted, in each phase of the discipline (PP, IP and FP) the three forms of assessment are considered. The presentation of the project and the oral argumentation (or QUIZ) results in individual evaluations, for the three phases. The PEER assessment is used to measure the skills development (Table 2). In this case, the perceptions of peers, the professor and the student self-assessment are considered.

The development of skills is related to the objective of the discipline in which the use of active methodologies occurs. The proposal presented in this work is based on the PSP4 (Production Systems Project 4) adapted from Reis et al. (2018) and can be adapted according to the context and methodology presented in the proposed discipline. The scope of PSP 4 involves the elaboration of a project with knowledge developed in the anchor discipline, Production Planning and Control (PCP), which is your corequisite at the 7th semester of the Industrial Engineering course.

Table 2 - List of skills to be developed during research project

Skills development (self evaluation / peer evaluation / professor evaluation)		
Team Work	Adaptability	Monitoring and Control of Deliveries
Collaboration	Conflict Management	Communication
Creativity	Relationship Building	Building Trust in the Team
Proactivity	Self-Management	Troubleshooting
Leadership	Self Confidence	Strategic Thought
Negotiation	Result Orientation	Technical contribution
Ethics and Values		

Source: Adapted from Reis et al. (2018)

This proposal contains dimensions of individual, group and peer evaluation, which were identified in the literature review. The gathering of these dimensions in this model seeks to bring a little of each methodology observed and compose a model with the expectation of considering individual technical and competence development, a gap commonly observed in active methodologies.

5 Final Considerations

Active learning has been widely supported by universities around the world. The works published on the subject point to positive results of learning and development of skills considered essential to the job market, such as leadership, teamwork, autonomy, problem solving, among others. However, there are some challenges to be overcome regarding the performance evaluation of students enrolled in disciplines with an active learning approach. Individual assessment in subjects with group projects is strongly mentioned, due to the difficulty in measuring the individual contribution of students to the projects.

In view of the above, this paper presents a literature review on the evaluation methodologies and criteria used and proposes an evaluation model that considers group activities, individual activities, self-evaluation, professor and peer evaluation. These dimensions were defined based on bibliographic research, teaching experience and in order to cover those different dimensions.

It is expected to provide a more reliable assessment result to the students' merit and also greater involvement in the activities to be developed. As a future work it is proposed to use games as a tool for evaluating technical content.

6 References

- Arbelaitz, O., Marti, J. I., & Muguerza, J. (2014). Analysis of introducing active learning methodologies in a basic computer architecture course. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 58(2), 110-116.
- Ashworth, D. W. (2011). Project Based Learning in International Teams—Monitoring the Effectiveness of Teamwork. In *Key Engineering Materials* (Vol. 450, pp. 581-584). Trans Tech Publications Ltd.
- CANALETA, Xavi et al. Master in teacher training: A real implementation of active learning. *Computers in human behavior*, v. 31, p. 651-658, 2014.
- Chang, S. H., Chen, M. L., Kuo, Y. K., & Shen, Y. C. (2011). A Simulation-Based LED Design Project in Photonics Instruction Based on Industry–University Collaboration. *IEEE Transactions on Education*, 54(4), 582-589.
- Chua, K. J., Yang, W. M., & Leo, H. L. (2014). Enhanced and conventional project-based learning in an engineering design module. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 24(4), 437-458.
- De los Ríos-Carmenado, I. G. N. A. C. I. O., Lopez, F. R., & Garcia, C. P. (2015). Promoting professional project management skills in engineering higher education: Project-based learning (PBL) strategy. *International journal of engineering education*, 31(1), 184-198.
- Herráez, M. A., & Claver, J. M. (2011). Assessment technique to encourage cooperative learning in a computer programming course. *The International journal of engineering education*, 27(4), 867-874.
- Krpalkova Krelova, K., Krpalek, P., & Kolarova, D. (2015). Developing entrepreneurial skills using project teaching. In *Rural Environment. Education. Personality.(REEP). Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference (Latvia)*. Latvia University of Agriculture.
- FERNANDES, Sandra. Preparing Graduates for Professional Practice: findings from a case-study of project-based learning (PBL). 2014.
- Fernandes, S., Mesquita, D., Flores, M. A., & Lima, R. M. (2014). Engaging students in learning: findings from a study of project-led education. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 39(1), 55-67.
- GARCIA, Isabel; DURAN, Alfonso; CASTRO, Manuel. Comparing the effectiveness of evaluating practical capabilities through hands-on online exercises versus conventional methods. In: 2008 38th Annual Frontiers in Education Conference. IEEE, 2008. p. F4H-18-F4H-22.
- Gweon, G., Jun, S., Finger, S., & Rosé, C. P. (2017). Towards effective group work assessment: even what you don't see can bias you. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, 27(1), 165-180.
- Krpalkova Krelova, K., Krpalek, P., & Kolarova, D. (2015). Developing entrepreneurial skills using project teaching. In *Rural Environment. Education. Personality.(REEP). Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference (Latvia)*. Latvia University of Agriculture.
- Leslie, L. J., & Gorman, P. C. (2017). Collaborative design of assessment criteria to improve undergraduate student engagement and performance. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 42(3), 286-301.
- Malheiro, B., Silva, M., Ribeiro, M. C., Guedes, P., & Ferreira, P. (2015). The European Project Semester at ISEP: the challenge of educating global engineers. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 40(3), 328-346.
- Nguyen, D. M., Truong, T. V., & Le, N. B. (2013, March). Deployment of capstone projects in software engineering education at duy tan university as part of a university-wide project-based learning effort. In *2013 Learning and Teaching in Computing and Engineering* (pp. 184-191). IEEE.
- Reis, A. C. B., Barbalho, S. C. M., de Araújo, F. L., Brito, L. S., Ishihara, S. E. M. P., & Teixeira, V. P. F. (2018). Project-Based Learning: development of PBL-based competencies under the pupil's perspective. In *10th International Symposium Project Approaches in Engineering Education (PAEE)*.
- Setiawan, A. W. (2019, April). Detailed Comparison of Instructor and Student-based Assessment in Project Based Learning. In *2019 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON)* (pp. 557-560). IEEE.
- Tao, J., Zhang, S., Yuan, Y., & Wen, X. (2015). Extending engineering specialty course concepts in electrical engineering education. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*, 52(1), 39-51.